

Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

D4.4 – Model Library Implementation and Recalibration of Adaptive Models I

WP4 Knowledge Management and Modelling in the
iHelp Platform

Dissemination Level: Public
Document type: Report
Version: 1.0
Date: April 29, 2022

The project iHelp has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme for research, technological development, and demonstration under grant agreement no 101017441.

Document Details

Project Number	101017441
Project Title	iHelp - Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records
Title of deliverable	Model Library Implementation and Recalibration of Adaptive Models I
Work package	WP4
Due Date	April 30, 2022
Submission Date	April 29, 2022
Start Date of Project	January 1, 2021
Duration of project	36 months
Main Responsible Partner	ICE-ES
Deliverable nature	Report
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Document Revision History

Version History			
Version	Date	Author(s)	Changes made
0.1	2022-02-21	Oscar Garcia Perales (ICE-ES)	Initial version of deliverable
0.2	2022-02-24	Oscar Garcia Perales (ICE-ES) José Gil López (ICE-ES)	Input to sections 3, 4.1 to 4.4.1
0.3	2022-03-01	Oscar Garcia Perales (ICE-ES) José Gil López (ICE-ES)	Input to sections 5.1 and 5.3
0.4	2022-03-07	Oscar Garcia Perales (ICE-ES)	Input to sections 1, 2 and 6
0.5	2022-03-16	Florin Picioara (SIE)	Input to section 3.6 and 4.4.2
0.6	2022-03-31	Alejandro Ramiro (LXS)	Input in section 5.2
0.7.1	2022-03-31	Pavlos Kranas (LXS)	1 st Review
0.7.2	2022-04-12	Giorgos Giotis (ATC)	2 nd Review
0.8	2022-04-19	Oscar Garcia Perales (ICE-ES) José Gil López (ICE-ES)	Address reviewers' comments and submit to Quality review
0.9	2022-04-26	Pavlos Kranas (LXS)	Quality review
1.0	2022-04-28	Dimosthenis Kyriazis (UPRC)	Final version

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Executive Summary

This deliverable summarizes the work that has been done in the core of T4.2 (“Model Library: Implementation and Recalibration of Adaptive Models”) until M16. This is the first version of a series of deliverables of this task, whose main objective is to provide details on how the developed prediction, prevention and intervention models will be stored and continuously refined or recalibrated based on the feedback gathered from the AI algorithms and user-centric applications.

The iHelp Analytic Workbench integrates a model library and a workbench in the iHelp Big Data Platform. The Analytic Workbench enables the “ingestion” of data analytics functions / tasks and their definition in a declarative way to enable the development of adaptive preventive and intervention models for different risks and contributing factors associated with Pancreatic Cancer. The implemented models are stored in a library within the iHelp Big Data platform that offers relevant APIs to support the continuous enrichment and/or adaptation of development models based on the availability and analysis of more (risk, predictions, feedback) data. The analytic workbench also facilitates openness and usability by allowing any actor (e.g. researcher, healthcare professional, data provider, etc.) to develop on-demand adaptive learning models for different risks based on the application of advance AI analytic techniques.

This deliverable is being released on M16 of the project and its main aim is to specify the Analytic Workbench along its functionalities. Moreover, the description on how to train and deploy any AI model will be provided so iHelp Clinician partners can train and deploy their own AI models to serve their own needs in the long run, kicking off this way the exploitation activities of the component. An updated and final version of this document will be released on M32.

1 Introduction

This document describes the developments carried out under task T4.2 to provide to the Data Scientists a workbench capable of selecting an algorithm (i.e., clustering) for training patient-related data and predicting the likelihood of developing pancreatic cancer according to the trained models.

This report is the first iteration of the deliverables to be produced in the context of the work that will be carried out in iHelp's task T4.2 ("Model Library: Implementation and Recalibration of Adaptive Models"). The main objective of this task is to integrate a model library and analytics workbench in the iHelp Big Data Platform. The Analytic Workbench enables the "ingestion" of data analytics functions/tasks and their definition in a declarative way to enable the development of adaptive, preventive, and intervention models for different risks and contributing factors associated with Pancreatic Cancer.

Besides the models developed and trained under the scope of the "*Personalised Health Modelling and Predictions*" and "*Early Risk Identification*" tasks which will be accessible through the Analytic Workbench, the current task will provide the possibility to train further models, belonging to the clustering family, so that more scenarios can be covered. Two paths will be provided for those parties interested in developing, training, and deploying their own models:

- A wizard-based way, by means of ICE AI & Analytics
- A script-based way, by means of Jupyter Notebooks.

In addition to this design-time activities, a runtime environment able to execute the different analytic models is being drafted. This runtime environment will be integrated in the iHelp Big Data Platform. Although in the different scenarios covered by iHelp, the runtime needs to deal with on-demand execution of analytic models of a particular patient, this runtime environment will offer also the possibility to connect to data streams, so the possibility of Real-Time Analytics is offered looking towards the post-project exploitation of the Analytic Workbench.

This document is organized as follows: Section 2 provides an introduction to the purpose and scope of the iHelp Analytic Workbench, while Section 3 describes ICE AI & Analytics which is the product selected as codebase for the development of iHelp Analytic Workbench. Section 4 provides the description on the algorithms that are being implemented for the clusterisation of the pancreatic cancer patients. Finally, Section 5 provides indications on the steps and integration with other iHelp components while Section 6 concludes this deliverable.

2 Purpose and Scope of the Analytic Workbench

The Analytic Workbench enables the “ingestion” of data analytics functions/tasks and their definition in a declarative way to enable the development of adaptive, preventive, and intervention models for different risks and contributing factors associated with Pancreatic Cancer.

Besides the models developed and trained under the scope of the “*Personalised Health Modelling and Predictions*” and “*Early Risk Identification*” tasks which will be accessible through the Analytic Workbench, the current task will provide the possibility to train further models, belonging to the clustering family, so that more scenarios can be covered.

The iHelp Analytic Workbench is based on the background technology brought by ICE, named AI & Analytics, which will be described in more detail in the following section. Besides AI & Analytics, the Analytic Workbench will be complemented with a module which will grant access to Jupyter Notebooks so that Data Scientists can write their own code.

Currently, ICE AI & Analytics is composed of the following modules:

- **A web-UI**, built using Angular, which will help the user in selecting the most appropriate ML algorithm for the problem
- **A collection of ML algorithms**: namely Deep Learning Encoder, Clustering, Regression, Convolutional Networks, etc.
- **A ML deployer** capable of packaging the models in an accessible way
- **An execution engine** based on Java and other Analytic engines, e.g., H2o.ai engine, for executing the deployed models in an easy way
- **A visualisation interface** where a good collection of data tables, charts, maps, and interactive resources can serve to visualise the results and get insights
- **A persistency layer** which is used to persist the data used and the different trained and deployed models
- **Hooks for data ingestion** which offers connectivity to several data pipes such as MQTT or AMQP

However, these modules are not enough to cover iHelp needs in terms of supporting other algorithms and, above all, executing them in a Kubernetes-based system. As such, besides training and helping the clinical partners in making use of the algorithms already present in the tool, the main developments that this task will carry over are the following:

- **Implement two new clustering algorithms**, namely Ward and Birch offered by scikit-learn
- **Develop an execution engine** capable of executing the models in a Kubernetes-like environment
- **Integrate algorithms** from other iHelp activities so they can be selected and executed
- **Integrate the Analytic Workbench** with other iHelp components
- **Integrate Jupyter Notebooks with the Analytic Workbench** to offer Data Scientists the possibility of writing their own analytic applications

The following table presents the functionality and accessibility of both sides of the Analytic Workbench at the same time that specifies the requirements for both hardware and software need to execute the Analytic Workbench.

Table 1: Analytic Workbench at a glance.

Design-Time	Functionality	The Design-time side of the Analytic Workbench will be in charge of training and parametrising analytical models for analysing data, in this case, from pancreatic cancer patients
	Accessibility	It is accessible via a web UI which will guide the user for creating the desired analytical models. In addition, it will contain a pointer to a module for Data Scientists who feel more comfortable in writing their own code via Jupyter Notebooks
Runtime	Functionality	The Runtime side of the Analytic Workbench will be in charge of executing the trained analytical models for predicting likeliness of suffering pancreatic cancer. Besides this, it will also plot the results once the analysis of the data is performed
	Accessibility	All trained models will be accessible via a REST API interface for their execution and for getting their results
Requirements	Hardware	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ VM 32Gb RAM ▪ 8 cores ▪ 350GB HD
	Software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Node 14.17 ▪ Python flask ▪ Docker ▪ Docker Compose ▪ git

3 Codebase of the Analytic Workbench

This section contains the detailed description of the iHelp Analytic Workbench, which is based on the background technology brought by ICE, named AI & Analytics. The iHelp Analytic Workbench will be also complemented with a module which will grant access to Jupyter Notebooks so that Data Scientists can write their own code.

3.1 Introduction

ICE AI & Analytics, which is the background technology of the iHelp Analytic Workbench, is a platform for training, adjusting, packaging, and executing analytic models. ICE AI & Analytics has been developed to extract value through the generation, training, and deployment of supervised and unsupervised analytic models.

The key features are:

- **Generate and trial run own models:** The model deployer is a space is used to upload the data, select a model, configure its parameters, and train it
- **Manage models:** The models generated are stored in an internal repository so they can be revisited/recalibrated as many times as possible
- **Connect data in real-time:** ICE AI & Analytics allows the trained models to be executed by using endpoints to connect to IoT devices. This will enable executing models in real time whilst ensuring security and privacy constraints. Most common data pipelines for real-time data, such as MQTT or AMQP, are supported
- **Supervised and unsupervised algorithms:** ICE AI & Analytics includes different algorithms which enable data situations to be evaluated and the results visualised to explore expected behaviour

The benefits ICE AI & Analytics offer are:

- **Design:** Design and configure Analytics models without programming knowledge
- **Connect:** Connect IoT data coming directly from the source
- **Explore:** Explore the data to be analysed before the ML model is deployed
- **Deploy:** Deploy the resulting model as a Java library to be included directly into applications
- **Visualise:** Visualise the results of the trained model and adjust the model
- **Support:** Critical infrastructure can be managed and supported by technical experts in the field

3.2 Algorithms available

The following is the list of algorithms that are currently available in the iHelp Analytic Workbench, classified by families:

- **Unsupervised algorithms:**
 - **Deep Learning Encoder** creates a model for anomaly detection based on either a group of columns or a single column, depending on the needs and features of the training dataset
 - **Clustering (K-means, etc.)** classifies the input data in a set of clusters
 - **Adaptive Heuristic for Opponent Classification (AdHoc)** is an algorithm that allows an agent to create classes of opponents while interacting with them

- **Supervised** algorithms
 - **Generalized Linear Models (GLM)** estimate regression models for outcomes following exponential distributions
- **Neural Networks** algorithms
 - **Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)** for automatically recognising objects in images
 - **Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)** for speech recognition and Natural Language Processing
 - **Restricted Boltzman Machines (RBMs)** for detecting inherent patterns automatically in the data by reconstructing the input
 - **Autoencoders** is used for reducing data dimensions by learning how to ignore the noise in the data

In the next phase, the two new algorithms (Birch and Ward) will be added to the side of K-means.

Figure 1: Clustering algorithms available in iHelp Analytic Workbench

3.3 Training a Model

Currently, the iHelp Analytic Workbench offers the possibility to train the different algorithms present in the platform. The way that models can be trained follows a wizard approach meaning that the user is guided across several forms to select the data to train and test, to select the columns, and parametrize the model to finally do the deploy of the model once it has been adjusted to the minimum error.

The following screens show how a K-Means model is trained. The first screen (Figure 2) shows the first step prior to train the K-Means model. This activity is performed by giving it a name and selecting the file to be used for the training of the algorithm.

Clustering algorithm H2O

Model name

e.g.: myModel, anomalies, tabberMachine_Jun2018, etc.

Training file

To train the model with a sample dataset

Figure 2: Preparing the K-means algorithm for a given dataset

Once the new model has a name and the training file is selected, in the next step (Figure 3) the header of the training file is shown and the Data Scientist is requested to select which of the columns contained in the file are the ones that should be selected for the actual training of the algorithm.

Clustering algorithms

Show entries First Previous **1** 2 3 4 5 ... 30 Next Last Search:

Showing 1 to 20 of 590 entries

<input type="checkbox"/> stage	<input type="checkbox"/> benign_sample_diagnosis	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> plasma_CA19_9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> creatinine	<input type="checkbox"/> LYVE1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> REG1B	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TFF1	<input type="checkbox"/> REG1A	<input type="checkbox"/>
NA	NA	11.7	1.83222	0.8932192	52.94884	654.282174	1262	no panc
NA	NA	NA	0.97266	2.037585	94.46703	209.48825	228.407	no panc
NA	NA	7	0.78039	0.1455889	102.366	461.141	NA	no panc
NA	NA	8	0.70122	0.00280488	60.579	142.95	NA	no panc
NA	NA	9	0.21489	0.00085956	65.54	41.088	NA	no panc
NA	NA	NA	0.84825	0.003393	62.126	59.793	NA	no panc
NA	NA	NA	0.62205	0.1743808	152.277	117.516	NA	no panc
NA	NA	11	0.89349	0.00357396	3.73	40.294	NA	no panc
NA	NA	NA	0.48633	0.00194532	7.021	26.782	NA	no panc
NA	NA	24	0.61074	0.2787785	83.928	19.185	NA	no panc
NA	NA	NA	0.29406	0.00117624	6.218	28.297	NA	no panc
NA	NA	23	1.05183	0.8603368	243.082	608.284	NA	no panc
NA	NA	NA	0.85956	1.416314	151.83077	74.1899025	505.571	no panc
NA	NA	7	1.91139	1.516773	150.89	590.686	NA	no panc
NA	NA	12	0.91611	0.5996449	93.811	93.576	NA	no panc
NA	NA	28	0.50895	0.0020358	24.366	19.698	NA	no panc
NA	NA	9	0.41847	0.00167388	17.102	0.03264066	NA	no panc
NA	NA	47	0.80301	0.00321204	3.588	30.071	NA	no panc
NA	NA	17	1.28934	2.285351	67.468	269.805	NA	no panc
NA	NA	8.7	0.50895	0.5830097	13.61906	267.193539	381	no panc

delete delete delete delete delete delete delete delete

Generating new dataset CSV

Figure 3: Selecting columns for the training of K-means algorithm for the selected dataset

Next step (Figure 4) requests the Data Scientist to parametrize the K-Means algorithm. The meaning of the different parameters is as follows:

- **Split dataset** specifies the size of the training/testing datasets. For example, when specifying a 0.75/0.25 split, H2o will split the dataset following the 0.75/0.25 ratios
- **Seed** specifies the Random Number Generator (RNG) for randomizing the execution of the algorithm
- **Init** specifies the initialization mode among the Random, Furthest, PlusPlus or User options:

- Random initialization randomly samples the k-specified value of the rows of the training data as cluster centers
- PlusPlus initialization randomly chooses one initial center and weights the random selection of subsequent centers so that points furthest from the first center are more likely to be chosen
- Furthest (default) initialization randomly chooses one initial center and then chooses the next center to be the furthest point away in terms of Euclidean distance
- User initialization requires the corresponding user points parameter. Note that the user-specified points dataset must have the same number of columns as the training dataset
- **Max Iterations** specifies the maximum number of iterations for the training phase. The default value is 10 and it ranges from 0 to 1000000
- **Clusters** specifies the number of clusters, or classes, to be classified
- **Normalize (Yes/No)** specifies whether the dataset has to be normalized or not. Since normalization is highly recommended, this option is enabled by default. If the dataset is not normalized, then the results can include components that are dominated by variables that appear to have larger variances relative to other attributes as a matter of scale, rather than true contribution

Clustering is a form of unsupervised learning that tries to find patterns or groups in the data without using any labels or target values

Split Dataset: <i>Required</i>	Seed: <i>Required</i>	Init: <i>Required</i>
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Max Iterations: <i>Required</i>	Clusters: <i>Required</i>	Normalize: <i>Required</i>
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Figure 4: Parametrizing the K-means algorithm for the selected dataset and columns

Figure 5: SS, AIC, and BIC curve

Figure 5 shows the Sum Squares (SS), the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and the Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) which will help in assessing which is the best cluster-size to predict. In the case shown in Figure 5, it can be understood that the best cluster is the 3rd one by looking at the yellow points in the three metrics represented as it is in this moment when a tradeoff between more clusters and computation is reached.

It is a system to automatically detect the classes that the training needs, then the algorithm automatically detects the classes of the columns of classes that have been selected in the input of classes. If the cluster property is left empty, the algorithm automatically detects the classes and works with that number of clusters. The graph is the graphical form of saying the number of clusters or classes needed and that number is the point that you see in it. For example, Figure 5 says that 3 clusters or classes are needed according to the training.

Figure 6 shows the original dataset, in a table, and its representation following a line chart plot. This way, the data scientist can explore if there are correlations between the different columns' data.

Figure 6: Columns selected and their relationship

Figure 7 shows the dispersion of the different classes' data. Each row belongs to a class and the selected algorithm has already grouped the data in clusters (see last column of the data table). The plot shows the result of the data table which needs to be revamped for easing the data interpretation.

Figure 7: Cluster predicted per row

Figure 8 show the best cluster to be predicted for each row and the dispersion of the different observations per row and column. As can be seen, many observations are accumulated in cluster 0 and 2; however, according to K-means guidelines from H2o.ai the trained model is not a good one as it has observations assigned to cluster 0 which is the test cluster.

Figure 8: Aggregated view of the clusters predicted per row

3.4 Deploying a Model

Once the model has been trained, it is ready to be deployed. Based on the capabilities of the ICE AI & Analytics, the iHelp Analytic Workbench can now automatically save the trained model in the workspace of the active user. This model can be further accessed for recalibration and deployment.

Figure 9: Models trained by the current user (My Models)

By accessing any of the models listed, they can be deployed in the target platform and the trained model can be finally configured by specifying which will be the input data pipeline and which will be the output data pipeline.

3.5 Advanced Analytics Workbench Notebook

To address experienced Data Scientists that have deep knowledge in ML programming languages, such as Python or Scala, an additional module is planned to be added to the iHelp Analytic Workbench.

This module aims to bring the following features via [Jupyter Notebook](#) open-source tool:

- Let the Data Scientist to wrangle the input data
- Training ML models with ML Python packages or Scala libraries
- Tracking ML models input parameters and performance metrics via [MLFlow](#) Tracking REST API
- Handling ML Models lifecycle (registering/versioning/reading) in MLFlow Repository via REST API.

The deployment of the ML Models will be done as:

- REST API
- Docker container via [Jupyter Kernel Gateway](#).

This is currently work in progress and thus, the documentation for the MLFlow, Jupyter Notebook and Jupyter Kernel Gateway will be included in future deliverables.

4 ML & AI Algorithms

This section contains the definition of the algorithms to be provided by the Analytic Workbench.

4.1 K-means (H2o.ai engine)

K-means clustering is a method for finding clusters and their centres in a set of unlabelled data. It is the obligation of the Data Scientist to choose the desired number of cluster centres, which usually it is determined by the nature of the data to analyse, and then the K-means procedure iteratively moves the centres to minimize the total within cluster variance.

Given an initial set of centres, the K-means algorithm alternates the two steps:

- For each centre, the subset of training points (its cluster) that is closer to it than any other centres are identified
- The means of each feature for the data points in each cluster are computed, and this mean vector becomes the new centre for that cluster.

These two steps are iterated until convergence. Typically, the initial centres are randomly chosen observations from the training data.

However, K-means can also be used in labelled data that needs to be classified according to clusters. The steps in this case are as follows:

- Apply K-means clustering to the training data in each class separately, using n prototypes per class
- Assign a class label to each of the $K \times n$ prototypes
- Classify a new feature x to the class of the closest prototype.

As mentioned above, the implementation of K-means within ICE AI & Analytics is the one inherited from H2o.ai libraries. Within H2o.ai, K-means falls in the general category of clustering algorithms as this is a form of unsupervised learning that tries to find structures in the data without using any labels or target values, falling thus under the clustering of unlabelled data. The algorithm splits a set of observations into separate groups such that an observation in a given group is more similar to another observation in the same group than to another observation in a different group.

Like in other implementations, within H2o.ai, K-means randomly chooses starting points and converges to a local minimum of centroids; however, the number of clusters is arbitrary and should be thought of as a tuning parameter. The output is a matrix of the cluster assignments and the coordinates of the cluster centres in terms of the originally chosen attributes. The cluster centres may differ slightly from run to run as this problem is Non-deterministic Polynomial-time (NP)-hard.

Each of the results obtained after the execution of K-means should be interpreted as follows:

- A graph of the scoring history which shows the number of iterations vs. within the cluster's sum of squares (SS)
- The output which includes the model category, validation metrics if applicable, and centres standard deviation

- The summary of the model which includes the number of clusters, number of categorical columns, number of iterations, the total within sum of squares, total sum of squares, total between the sum of squares
- The scoring history meaning the duration, number of iterations, number of reassigned observations, and number of within cluster sum of squares
- The training metrics which include the model's name, checksum name, frame name, frame checksum name, description if applicable, model category, scoring time, predictions, mean square error (MSE), root mean square error (RMSE), total within sum of squares, total sum of squares, and total between sum of squares
- The statistics of the centroids meaning their number, size, within cluster sum of squares
- The means of each cluster which include the centroid number, and the columns

4.2 Birch (Scikit-learn engine)

Clustering algorithms like K-means clustering do not perform clustering very efficiently and it is difficult to process large datasets with a limited number of resources (like memory or a slower CPU). So, regular clustering algorithms do not scale well in terms of running time and quality as the size of the dataset increases. This is where BIRCH clustering comes in.

Balanced Iterative Reducing and Clustering using Hierarchies (BIRCH) is a clustering algorithm that can cluster large datasets by first generating a small and compact summary of the large dataset. This smaller and more compact dataset is meant to retain as much information as possible from the original dataset and it is precisely this summary which is then clustered instead of clustering the larger dataset. Hence, BIRCH is a scalable clustering method based on hierarchy clustering and only requires a one-time scan of the dataset, making it fast for working with large datasets.

In a nutshell, it converts data to a tree data structure with the centroids being read off the leaf. And these centroids can be the final cluster centroid or the input for other cluster algorithms. However, BIRCH has one major drawback – it can only process metric attributes. A **metric attribute** is any attribute whose values can be represented in Euclidean space i.e., no categorical attributes should be present.

Two important terms from BIRCH need to be clarified to fully understand the algorithm:

- As said, BIRCH summarizes large datasets into smaller, dense regions. These regions are called **Clustering Feature (CF)** entries and they allow comparison between each other. Formally, a Clustering Feature entry is defined as an ordered triple, (N, LS, SS) where 'N' is the number of data points in the cluster, 'LS' is the linear sum of the data points and 'SS' is the squared sum of the data points in the cluster.
- The **CF Tree** is the actual compact representation of a tree where each leaf node contains a sub-cluster. Every entry in a CF tree contains a pointer to a child node and a CF entry made up of the sum of CF entries in the child nodes. There is a maximum number of entries in each leaf node. This maximum number is called the threshold.

The iHelp Analytic Workbench will incorporate the Scikit-learn implementation of BIRCH where a tree called the Clustering Feature Tree (CFT) for the given data will be built. The data is essentially lossy compressed to a set of Clustering Feature nodes (CF Nodes). The CF Nodes have a number of subclusters

called Clustering Feature subclusters (CF Subclusters) and these CF Subclusters located in the non-terminal CF Nodes can have CF Nodes as children.

The CF Subclusters hold the necessary information for clustering which prevents the need to hold the entire input data in memory. This information includes:

- Number of samples in a subcluster
- An n-dimensional vector holding the sum of all samples called *Linear Sum*
- The sum of the squared L2 norm of all samples called *Squared Sum*
- *Centroids* to avoid recalculation of *Linear Sum* / *n_samples*
- Squared norm of the centroids.

The BIRCH algorithm has two parameters, the **threshold** and the **branching factor**. The branching factor limits the number of subclusters in a node while the threshold limits the distance between the entering sample and the existing subclusters.

4.3 Ward (Scikit-learn engine)

A clustering algorithm like K-means is good for clustering tasks as it is fast and easy to implement but it has limitations that it works well if data can be grouped into globular or spherical clusters and also one needs to provide a number of clusters. Since K-means is based on Euclidean distances from the cluster centre to point in the cluster, it will be able to cluster data that is organized according to globular or spherical shapes while it will fail to cluster data that is organized in a different manner.

Hierarchical clustering is a kind of clustering that uses either top-down or bottom-up approach in creating clusters from data. It either starts with all samples in the dataset as one cluster and goes on dividing that cluster into more clusters or it starts with single samples in the dataset as clusters and then merges samples based on criteria to create clusters with more samples.

The results of clustering can be visualised as a dendrogram as hierarchical clustering progress. This helps in deciding when to stop clustering further (how "deep") by setting "depth" with some threshold.

It has two types:

- **Agglomerative Clustering** (bottom-up approach) which starts with single samples and clusters and keeps on combining them into clusters until a single cluster is left.
- **Divisive Clustering** (top-down approach) which starts with the whole dataset as one cluster and then keeps on dividing it into small clusters until each one consists of a single sample.

To understand agglomerative clustering and divisive clustering, it is necessary to understand the concepts of **single linkage** and **complete linkage**. While single linkage helps in deciding the similarity between 2 clusters which can then be merged into one cluster, complete linkage helps with divisive clustering which is based on dissimilarity measures between clusters. Divisive Clustering chooses the object with the maximum average dissimilarity and then moves all objects to this cluster that are more similar to the new cluster than to the remainder.

ICE AI & Analytics will incorporate the Scikit-learn implementation of Ward where it minimizes the sum of squared distance between all pairs of clusters. It is a variance-minimizing approach and in this sense is similar to the k-means objective function but tackled with an agglomerative hierarchical approach. In

scikit-learn the agglomerative clustering is taken as default as it initiates the clustering from the bottom, i.e. each observation is assigned to its own cluster, and progresses to the top by merging clusters. The linkage criterion determines the metric used for the merge strategy:

- **Single Linkage** minimizes the distance between the closest observations of pairs of clusters.
- **Complete Linkage** minimizes the maximum distance between observations of pairs of clusters.
- **Average Linkage** minimizes the average of the distances between all observations of pairs of clusters.

4.4 Algorithms provided via Advanced Analytics Workbench

Experienced Data Analyst will interact with Advanced Workbench Notebook via a web interface provided based on a Jupyter Notebook running as server. This Advanced Workbench Notebook will be accessed through the iHelp Analytic Workbench, and the models trained in it will be accessible through the *My Model* view (Figure 9).

Both Notebook Interface and the model serving REST API are based on Docker image that is built with following ML algorithms packages included:

- [Scikit-Learn](#)
- [TensorFlow](#)

Therefore, the Data Scientist can use in the Notebooks any algorithm included in this package. Moreover, if need it, the Docker Image can be extended, and new ML algorithm packages will be added to the Analytic Workbench. The REST APIs to access these Docker images are still under definition and will be included in the next iteration of this deliverable.

This flexibility is the power of this tool. It can be viewed also as a weakness since it required advanced knowledge both in Python programming and Machine Learning algorithms.

4.5 Other Algorithms

4.5.1 Integration of Other Algorithms into Analytic Workbench

For easing the integration of other AI/ML algorithms coming from iHelp partners, the following JSON file specifies which are the different parameters that the trained models from other iHelp partners can be easily integrated into the Analytic Workbench.

However, the JSON specified below will be subject to changes to accommodate feedback from iHelp partners.

```
{
  "version": "0.1",
  "call": {
    "params": {
      "nameModel": "Clustering_H2O.202202252",
      "patientID": "ID",
      "age": "34",
      "gender": "man"
    },
    "return": {
      "status": "finished",
      "retrainModel": true,
    }
  }
}
```

```

        "responseColumnName": "columnsPredicsModel",
        "level": "critical"
    },
    "typeRest": "GET",
    "urlExec": "/getModelBirch/{modelName}/{patientID}",
    "ipRestAPI": "http://ipRestAPI",
    "port": 8000
},
"algorithm": "Kmeans",
"timestamp": "22-02-26 12:31:29,573",
"partner": "ICE",
"values": [],
"viewMetrics": false,
"metrics": {
    "MAE": 8.317474074051735,
    "MSE": 137.29634505748047,
    "RMSE": 11.717352305767735,
    "RMSLE": 0.01741955162201051,
    "r2": 0.8843442430836354,
    "AIC": 58016.14022134703,
    "customMetricName": null,
    "customMetricValue": 0.0,
    "residualDeviance": 1026290.1793046666,
    "meanResidualDeviance": 137.29634505748047,
    "nullDeviance": 8874260.619064769,
    "nullDegreesOfFreedom": 7474
}
}

```

The JSON file is composed of the following sections:

- **version:** specifies the version of the JSON file
- **call:** contains the information needed for the execution of the model. This includes the following subitems:
 - **params** is composed of the different parameters for calling the model, i.e., the name of the model (**nameModel**), the ID of the patient (**patientID**), the age of the patient (**age**) and their gender (**gender** = {*male, female, ...*})
 - **return** is composed of the different variables after executing the model, i.e., the status of the execution (**status** = {*running, finished, awaiting*}), if the model has been retrained (**retrainModel** = {*true, false*}), the column with the response of the prediction of the disease (**disease**), and the level of criticality (**level** = {*critical, non-critical, ...*})
 - **typeRest** specifies the type of REST call verb. This parameter can take either GET or POST REST methods
 - **urlExec** specifies the path for executing the model
 - **ipRestAPI** specifies the URL base for executing the model
 - **port** specifies the port where the model will be listening for execution
- **algorithm:** specifies which is the algorithm to be executed
- **timestamp:** specifies the date/time when the model was created
- **partner:** specifies which is the iHelp partner that has created the model
- **values:** is a wildcard to specify some extra parameters that might be needed for the execution of the algorithm. As an example, for a k-means it could be the names of other columns used for the prediction of the clusters

- **viewMetrics:** specifies if any of the metrics from the next group is expected to be received
- **metrics:** specifies several metrics computed when training the model. Please, note that not all the entries under metrics are mandatory for all models but some might be depending on the model trained. These entries are:
 - Mean Absolute Error (MAE)
 - Mean Square Error (MSE)
 - Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)
 - Root Mean Square Log Error (RMSLE)
 - R-Square (R^2)
 - Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)
 - Custom Metric Name
 - Custom Metric Value
 - Residual Deviance
 - Mean Residual Deviance
 - Null Deviance
 - Null Degrees of Freedom

4.5.2 iHelp AI Models & Algorithms

Various ML models are implemented in the context of tasks T4.1 & T5.1. Specifically, a Logistic Regression (LR) model, which is a linear model for classification, is provided. In this model, the probabilities describing the possible outcomes of a single trial are modelled using a logistic function. In terms of fine-tuning the parameters of the LR model various solvers are considered like the “liblinear”, “newton-cg” and “lbfgs”. Moreover, a LogisticRegressionCV model that implements Logistic Regression with built-in cross-validation support, to find the optimal parameters according to the scoring attribute is also considered.

Tree based models are also provided like a Decision Trees (DT) model, a Random Forest (RF) model and a Gradient Tree Boosting or Gradient Boosted Decision Trees (GBDT) model. DT model is a non-parametric supervised learning method used for classification and regression. A DT classifier model is used to perform multi-class classification on the historical EHR datasets. The rest of the tree-based models actually belong to the family of ensemble ML methods, where predictions from several base estimators built with a given learning algorithm are combined in order to improve generalizability over a single estimator. The RF classifier builds several estimators (DT estimators) independently and then computes the average of their predictions. The combined estimator usually performs better than any of the individual estimators because its variance is reduced. The GBDT model combines several weak models to produce a powerful ensemble. In this case the base estimators are built sequentially and each one tries to reduce the bias of the combined estimator.

Models based on neural networks (NN) are also implemented driven by the motivation that NN are able to capture more complex patterns in the training data. Specifically, a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) model is provided consisting of two hidden layers. MLP models are suitable for classification prediction problems where inputs are assigned a class. The fact that some of the data are actually timestamped events creates the need to implement also a NN model capable of capturing long-term dependencies between the data events. For this reason, a Long short-term memory (LSTM) model is also considered. The LSTM model belongs to the family of recurrent NNs.

5 Integration with other iHelp Modules

This section provides a list of the requirements of the different modules that will be implemented during the iHelp project. These requirements are related with specific component portions, which can be either a program, a software component, an existing product that will be used as part of the overall platform, or a set of combinations of all the above, that implements a specific functionality and provides a set of capabilities via well-defined interfaces.

5.1 REST APIs

The Analytic Workbench will be called and accessed by several iHelp modules and, to facilitate this activity, several REST APIs will be provided. As such, the following are the REST API calls available for calling the different trained models in the Analytic Workbench by the any iHelp component.

Table 2: Login

Section	Description
REST Verb	POST
URL	/token
Description	Login For Access Token Authorisation
Input Parameters	<p><i>User</i>: user to access the models <i>Pass</i>: password corresponding to the user</p> <pre>{ "user": "pavlos@leanxcale.com", "pass": "Kranas.1234" }</pre>
Return Object	<p>Token with an expiry time of 30 minutes</p> <pre>{ "access_token": "eyJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiIsInR5cCI6IkpXVCJ9.eyJzdWIiOiJhZG1pb2IIsImV4cCI6MTY1MDM2MTkzMn0.CDTc3DnB-xVIO0u7uQi_voFwENBFerjnFjgQhk4Chk", "token_type": "bearer" }</pre>

Table 3: List all Models

Section	Description
REST Verb	GET
URL	/listModels
Description	Read list models in repositories
Input Parameters	None

Return Object	<p>List models in repository</p> <pre>{ "Clustering_Birch.20220215_birch_model.pkl", "Clustering_H2O.202203011", "Clustering_H2O.202203012", "Clustering_H2O.202203013", "Clustering_H2O.202203014", "Clustering_sklearn.20220218_model.pkl", "Clustering_Ward.20220215_Average_model.pkl", "Clustering_Ward.20220215_Complete_model.pkl", "Clustering_Ward.20220215_Single_model.pkl", "Clustering_Ward.20220215_Wards_model.pkl" }</pre>
----------------------	--

Table 4: Get a given Model

Section	Description
REST Verb	GET
URL	/getModel/{modelName}
Description	Obtain the model chosen by the parameters
Input Parameters	<p><i>modelName</i>: Name of the model</p> <pre>{ "modelName": "Clustering_H2O.202203011" }</pre>
Return Object	<p>Trained columns of the selected model</p> <pre>{ "age", "sex", "stage", "plasma_CA19_9", "creatinine", "LYVE1", "REG1B", "TFF1", "REG1A" }</pre>

Table 5: Get prediction (with a K-means model) of a given patient

Section	Description
REST Verb	GET
URL	/execModelKMeans/{modelName}/{patient}
Description	Obtain the prediction of a K-Means model and patient identified by the parameters

Input Parameters	<i>modelName</i> : Name of the model <i>patient</i> : ID of the patient
Return Object	Object with the ID of the model to be executed <pre>{ "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "patientID": "1", "typeAlgorithm": "k-means" }</pre>
	Object with the prediction of the selected patient <pre>{ "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "predict": "Kidney renal clear cell carcinoma", "patientID": "1", "risk": "high", "date": "20220101", "accuracy": "20220101", "typeAlgorithm": "k-means" }</pre>

Table 6: Get prediction (with a BIRCH model) of a given patient

Section	Description
REST Verb	GET
URL	/execModelBirch/{modelName}/{patient}
Description	Obtain the prediction of a BIRCH model and patient identified by the parameters
Input Parameters	<i>modelName</i> : Name of the model <i>patient</i> : ID of the patient
Return Object	Object with the ID of the model to be executed <pre>{ "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "patientID": "1", "typeAlgorithm": "birch" }</pre>
	Object with the prediction of the selected patient <pre>{ "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "predict": "Kidney renal clear cell carcinoma", "patientID": "1", "risk": "high", "date": "20220101", "accuracy": "20220101", "typeAlgorithm": "birch" }</pre>

Table 7: Get prediction (with a WARD model) of a given patient

Section	Description
REST Verb	GET
URL	<code>/execModelWard/{modelName}/{patient}</code>
Description	Obtain the prediction of a WARD model and patient identified by the parameters
Input Parameters	<i>modelName</i> : Name of the model <i>patient</i> : ID of the patient
Return Object	Object with the ID of the model to be executed
	<pre>{ "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "patientID": "1", "typeAlgorithm": "ward" }</pre>
	Object with the prediction of the selected patient
	<pre>{ "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "predict": "Kidney renal clear cell carcinoma", "patientID": "1", "risk": "high", "date": "20220101", "accuracy": "20220101", "typeAlgorithm": "ward" }</pre>

Table 8: Get prediction (with a WARD model, Complete Linkage variant) of a given patient

Section	Description
REST Verb	GET
URL	<code>/execModelComplete/{modelName}/{patient}</code>
Description	Obtain the prediction of a WARD model and patient identified by the parameters using Complete Linkage
Input Parameters	<i>modelName</i> : Name of the model <i>patient</i> : ID of the patient
Return Object	Object with the ID of the model to be executed
	<pre>{ "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "patientID": "1", "typeAlgorithm": "wardComplete" }</pre>
	Object with the prediction of the selected patient
	<pre>{</pre>

	<pre> "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "predict": "Kidney renal clear cell carcinoma", "patientID": "1", "risk": "high", "date": "20220101", "accuracy": "20220101", "typeAlgorithm": "wardComplete" } </pre>
--	---

Table 9: Get prediction (with a WARD model, Single Linkage variant) of a given patient

Section	Description
REST Verb	GET
URL	<code>/execModelSingle/{modelName}/{patient}</code>
Description	Obtain the prediction of a WARD model and patient identified by the parameters using Single Linkage
Input Parameters	<i>modelName</i> : Name of the model <i>patient</i> : ID of the patient
Return Object	Object with the ID of the model to be executed <pre> { "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "patientID": "1", "typeAlgorithm": "wardSingle" } </pre>
	Object with the prediction of the selected patient <pre> { "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "predict": "Kidney renal clear cell carcinoma", "patientID": "1", "risk": "high", "date": "20220101", "accuracy": "20220101", "typeAlgorithm": "wardSingle" } </pre>

Table 10: Get prediction (with a WARD model, Average Linkage variant) of a given patient

Section	Description
REST Verb	GET
URL	<code>/execModelAverage/{modelName}/{patient}</code>
Description	Obtain the prediction of a WARD model and patient identified by the parameters using Single Linkage
Input Parameters	<i>modelName</i> : Name of the model

	<i>patient</i> : ID of the patient
Return Object	Object with the ID of the model to be executed <pre>{ "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "patientID": "1", "typeAlgorithm": "wardAverage" }</pre>
	Object with the prediction of the selected patient <pre>{ "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "predict": "Kidney renal clear cell carcinoma", "patientID": "1", "risk": "high", "date": "20220101", "accuracy": "20220101", "typeAlgorithm": "wardAverage" }</pre>

Table 11: Get execution status

Section	Description
REST Verb	GET
URL	<code>/getStatusModel/{jobID}</code>
Description	Obtain the status of the execution of a model
Input Parameters	<i>jobID</i> : ID of the executing model
Return Object	Object with the status of the executing model <pre>{ "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "patientID": "1", "typeAlgorithm": "k-means", "status": "queued" }</pre>

Table 12: Get graph URL

Section	Description
REST Verb	GET
URL	<code>/getGraph/{jobID}</code>
Description	Obtain the URL pointing to the graph generated after the execution of the model
Input Parameters	<i>jobID</i> : ID of the executing model

Return Object	Object with the URL of the graph
	<pre data-bbox="659 264 1401 521"> { "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "patientID": "1", "urlBase": "https://ihelp.icelab.cloud/superset/explore" "graphPath": "/?form_data_key=pfHz95ZsamsZXQLfJnKq08p_93xU9rQZCkJvri3nJFvSmAdsYbjGxelegLHdUatu&standalone=1&height=400" }</pre>

5.2 Big Data Platform

The Big Data Platform provides the data management layer of the iHelp integrated solution which allows for the persistent storage and retrieval of raw data, training models, analytical algorithms, intermediate or final results of their execution and any other meta-information required by the several components of the platform. Based on its unique characteristics, it allows for data ingestion at very high rates, using different approaches like the *Change Data Capture* paradigm that enables the so-called **data offloading** from an external data source into the Big Data Platform. Having that healthcare organizations, institutions or hospitals can send a vast amount of data to the Big Data Platform, which can ingest this information very efficiently. What is more, it provides analytical capabilities, allowing the data analysts to execute AI algorithms, like the ones described in the previous sections, which can push down the data pre-processing to the datastore and gather aggregated information that can feed the models. In that sense, the Big Data Platform can be used to retrieve row data in an efficient manner.

Moreover, the Big Data Platform can be used to store the models defined and trained by the data analysts through the iHelp Analytic Workbench and provide the means for the latter to retrieve them and serve them to the DSS layer, so that the clinicians or other data users can be aware of. As such, it can be used as the persistence layer of the iHelp Analytic Workbench.

What is more, the training models, or the AI algorithms themselves can produce intermediate or final results, which can feed other algorithms in a data pipeline or can be stored to be visualized by the iHelp graph at a later phase. Or even other meta-information that several algorithms or components that interact with each other via the Analytic Workbench might need. As a result, the Big Data Platform can be considered as the persistent layer of the overall iHelp integrated solution and stores and retrieves data for/to various components, requested by the Analytic Workbench. For the integration of the latter with the Big Data Platform, there are several means for data connectivity that have been provided that will be examined in this subsection.

Firstly, the Big Data Platform contains a relational query engine that is compliant to standard SQL and implements the standard data connectivity mechanisms: it provides both a JDBC and an ODBC driver, along with a python SQLAlchemy driver. In that case, we might have AI algorithms that are being instantiated and being executed into the runtime execution environment of the iHelp Analytic Workbench and need to interact with the Big Data Platform in order to consume raw HHR data or to store intermediate or final results. These algorithms can be informed during the runtime by the Workbench about the configuration details of the data store (i.e., connection URL, port, logical database name or schema, etc.) and then make use of the aforementioned data connectivity mechanisms to open a database connection and interact with the datastore. Both JDBC and ODBC drivers are standardised ways

for interacting with a datastore, while the python driver can be used by any AI technology written in python. Moreover, the Big Data Platform additionally provides a Spark connector, which can be loaded by a Spark program. It encapsulates the details for data connectivity to the connector and let the data user or data analyst to make use of the Spark API.

Moreover, the Big Data Platform implements the OData specification, which is an OASIS standard that defines REST API for interacting with a data management layer. It makes use of an internal *entity model* that can requested to retrieve information from (using a ‘*get*’ operation over the primary field, or ‘*filter*’ conditions over the entire dataset) or store (insert, update, upsert, delete) to. The *entity model* for the Big Data Platform is the logical schema of the data base, and therefore, the data user can use this standard REST API to interact. There are also various client implementations for this standard, with the Apache Olingo being one of the most popular.

Last but not least, the iHelp Analytic Workbench makes use of Kafka brokers to let AI algorithms to interchange data between them. The output of one algorithm can be feed to a specific Kafka topic that the second algorithm listens to. When data is available in this topic, it can be retrieved from the second algorithm and be used as its input. Kafka brokers can be also used for the interaction of the iHelp Workbench with the Big Data Platform in a similar way: the Workbench retrieves that output of an AI algorithm and puts it to a Kafka topic, as before. At this case, instead of the data to be further forwarded to the next algorithm in the data pipeline, it can be persistently stored to the datastore. The iHelp Big Data Platform provides a Kafka connector that can be used to transparently store data that arrives to a specific topic to a target data table of the database. In the scope of task T4.4 (“Big Data Platform and Knowledge Management System”), a Kafka broker which includes this connector has been provided and can be used by the iHelp Analytic Workbench. More information will be found at the D4.10, which however is planned to be delivered in M22. Therefore, the details for configuring such a connector are given here, to be used as a reference to the data users of application developers using the iHelp Analytic Workbench. An example of its use can be found in the following code snippet:

```
name=local-lx-sink-output
connector.class=com.leanxcale.connector.kafka.LXSinkConnector
tasks.max=1
topics=output-lxs

connection.properties=lx://ihelp-store:9876/HHR@APP;KVPROXY=ihelp-store!9800
auto.create=true
batch.size=500
connection.check.timeout=20

key.converter=io.confluent.connect.avro.AvroConverter
key.converter.schema.registry.url=http://localhost:8081
value.converter=io.confluent.connect.avro.AvroConverter
value.converter.schema.registry.url=http://localhost:8081

sink.connection.mode=kivi
sink.transactional=false

insert.mode=upsert

table.name.format=patients
pk.mode=record_key
pk.fields=patient_id
fields.whitelist=firstname, lastname, age, birthdata
```

The following parameters must be configured when starting the Kafka broker:

- **name**: the name of the connector that will be given upon its instantiation
- **topics**: the topic that the connector will listen to
- **connection.properties**: the connection URL for the connector to connect the datastore
- **table.name.format**: the name of the target table
- **pk.fields**: the names of the columns that consist the primary key
- **fields.whitelist**: the names of the columns that the data user needs to store to the data table. If this is empty, all columns will be stored

The Kafka connector assumes that data being added to the Kafka topic are being encrypted using the Apache Avro Schema Registry, which is included into the Kafka images provided by T4.4. This is not mandatory, and the data user should define the corresponding key and value converters. However, we strongly recommend the use of the Avro Converter that can transmit data much more efficiently.

5.3 iHelp Decision Support System

The iHelp Decision Support System (DSS) component will use the Analytic Workbench to request the execution of the different AI/ML algorithms so that the clinicians can evaluate the data from the patients to assess of the likelihood of having pancreatic cancer. As such, the DSS will trigger the execution of any of the AI/ML algorithms present in the Analytic Workbench.

The iHelp DSS will connect to the Analytic Workbench by the following means:

- **Executing an algorithm** (see Table 5 to Table 10): this call will require the following parameters:
 - Type of algorithm/model to be executed
 - Parameters of the call, like patient ID, age, cigarettes, etc.
 - Result being the identifier of the execution call.
- **Status of the execution** (see Table 11): this call will require the following parameters:
 - Identifier of the execution (obtained from the previous call)
 - Result being the status of the execution. This can take one of the following values: *queued, running, finished...*
- **Get the result graph** (see Table 12): this call will require the following parameters:
 - Identifier of the execution (obtained from the first call)
 - Result being the URL where the chart generated by the Analytic Workbench is accessible after the execution of the model.

5.4 Personalised Health Modelling and Early Risk Identification

The Analytic Workbench provides the execution runtime for the models produced in tasks T4.1 and T5.1. The internal architecture of the predictive analytics components follows an asynchronous execution model as it is depicted in Figure 10. The *trigger_analysis* API creates a new task that is placed in a job queue. A worker process continuously listens to that job queue and whenever a new task is available, it gets processed. A unique identifier binds an analysis request to its results.

Figure 10: Internal architecture of iHelp predictive components

The *trigger_analysis* and *get_results* API calls will be wrapped in the following REST API methods exposed by the Analytic Workbench:

Table 13: Execute iHelp model URL

Section	Description
REST Verb	GET
URL	/execiHelpModel/{modelName}/{patient}
Description	Obtain the prediction of a model and patient identified by the parameters
Input Parameters	<p><i>modelName</i>: Name of the model. Available models are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ LR (Logistic Regression) ▪ DT (Decision Trees) ▪ RF (Random Forests) ▪ GBDT (Gradient Boosted Decision Trees) ▪ MLP (Multilayer Perceptron) ▪ LSTM (Long short-term memory) <p><i>patient</i>: ID of the patient</p>
Return Object	<p>Object with the ID of the model to be executed</p> <pre>{ "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "patientID": "1", "typeAlgorithm": "Random forest" }</pre>

	<p>Object with the prediction of the selected patient</p> <pre>{ "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "patientID": "1", "date": "20220101", "typeAlgorithm": "Random forest" }</pre>
--	--

Table 14: Get iHelp model status and results URL

Section	Description
REST Verb	GET
URL	/getStatusModel/{jobID}
Description	Obtain the status of the execution of a model
Input Parameters	<i>jobID</i> : ID of the executing model
Return Object	<p>Object with the status of the executing model</p> <pre>{ "jobID": "12093cf8-2ebd-4be9-81eb-92dc3cf0ed82", "patientID": "1", "typeAlgorithm": "Random forest", "status": "completed", "risk": "high", "accuracy": "20220101" }</pre>

6 Conclusions

This document summarises the developments carried out in the scope of T4.2 (“Model Library: Implementation and Recalibration of Adaptive Models”) of the project for preparing the Analytic Workbench environment to help Clinicians and Data Scientists in selecting, training, deploying, and executing the ML/AI algorithms that better fit their needs. As such, it will be based on ICE AI & Analytics product as the background technology and will include several improvements and additions that are being currently incorporating to cover the scenarios and needs of clinicians, as identified by the user requirements (D2.1) of the project. The improvements include the integration of Jupyter Notebooks that allow the more proficient Data Scientists to write their own Python scripts. Besides this major improvement and to cover other aspects and other analytical needs, ICE AI & Analytics will also incorporate other algorithms developed under the scope of the project so they can be selected and executed in the same way that they would have been developed by the clinicians themselves.

Finally, the Analytic Workbench has started also its integration with other iHelp components to ensure that the predictions calculated by the different algorithms are taken down the decision path for the Clinicians or, at least, are stored for later use. In this sense, both the iHelp Big Data Platform and the iHelp DSS are provided with a set of REST APIs to access the different data and algorithm’s information.

This is the first iteration of two documents that are planned to be released through the project. This first version establishes the baseline for the development of the Analytic Workbench and the different activities for its development. While next iteration will focus on the integration activities and on the runtime, this one focuses on the design time and on the definition of the REST APIs for accessing the Analytic Workbench when it is time for integration.

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List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
ATC	Athens Technology Centre
BIC	Bayesian Information Criterion
BIRCH	Balanced Iterative Reducing and Clustering using Hierarchies
CF	Clustering Feature
CFT	Clustering Feature Tree
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
DSS	Decision Support System
DT	Decision Trees
EHR	Electronic Health Records
ENG	Engineering Ingegneria Informatics SpA
EU	European Union
FPG	Agostino Gemelli University Policlinic
GBDT	Gradient Boosted Decision Trees
GLM	Generalized Linear Models
HD	Hard disk
HDM	Hospital de Denia-MarinaSalud
HHR	Holistic Health Records
ICE	Information Catalyst for Enterprise
INS	Innovation Sprint
IoT	Internet of Things
JDBC	Java Database Connectivity
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KI	Karolinska Institutet
KOD	KODAR Systems
LR	Logistic Regression
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
LXS	LeanXcale
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MSE	Mean Square Error
MUP	Medical University Plovdiv
NN	Neural Networks
NP	Non-deterministic Polynomial-time
ODBC	Open Database Connectivity
PC	Pancreatic Cancer
RBM	Restricted Boltzman Machines
REST	Representational State Transfer

RF	Random Forest
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RMSLE	Root Mean Square Log Error
RNG	Random Number Generator
RNN	Recurrent Neural Networks
SIE	Siemens
SQL	Structured Query Language
SS	Sum Squares
TMU	Taipei Medical University
UI	User Interface
UNIMAN	University of Manchester
UPM	Universidad Politecnica de Madrid
UPRC	University of Piraeus Research Centre
URL	Universal Resource Identifier
VM	Virtual Machine